

Generalized Dicke states, or density matrix description of N 2-level atoms homogeneously coupled to the environment

G. A. Kazakov

Abstract

Here I describe in brief how to treat fully homogeneous system of N equal 2-level atoms coupled to the field of bad cavity. Consideration is based primarily on the paper [1] but restricted to fully symmetric states only, and does not employ $SU(4)$ group theory explicitly.

1 General considerations

Consider some generic system consisting of N 2-level atoms homogeneously coupled to the bath and (optionally) to another part of the system. If the atoms were initially in some symmetric state, then, in the absence of relaxations, their state remains symmetric in all the subsequent points of time. So, without relaxations the system of such atoms can be described as an effective “particle” with total pseudospin equal to $N/2$ (for composite system consisting of such atoms plus something also, the state Ψ of the whole system may be decomposed into $|\Psi\rangle = \sum_{m,k} c_{mk} |\psi_m\rangle \otimes |\phi_k\rangle$, where $\{|\psi_m\rangle\}$ are symmetric pure states of the atoms (say, m is a z -projection of the pseudospin), and $\{|\phi_m\rangle\}$ are some basis states describing another part of the system). Further we will consider the system consisting on the atoms only, because, first, generalization to the composite systems is straightforward, and, second, we consider bad-cavity laser with adiabatically eliminated cavity field.

If the atoms interact with some bath, they should be described by density matrix instead of the wave function, and this density matrix, generally speaking, can not be decomposed into $\sum_{m,k} |\psi_m\rangle\langle\psi_k|$ [1]. However, the density matrix itself should keep the permutation symmetry.

It is convenient to introduce operators

$$\hat{u}_i = \hat{\sigma}_{ee}^i \quad \hat{d}_i = \hat{\sigma}_{gg}^i \quad \hat{s}_i = \hat{\sigma}_{eg}^i \quad \hat{c}_i = \hat{\sigma}_{ge}^i \quad (1)$$

We suppose that the atoms are initially in fully symmetric state. Then their density matrix also will be

fully symmetric, and may be represented as

$$\hat{\rho} = \sum_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \rho_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}, \quad \text{where} \quad (2)$$

$$\hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} = S(\hat{u}^\alpha \hat{d}^\beta \hat{s}^\gamma \hat{c}^\delta) \equiv \frac{1}{C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}} \sum_p \hat{O}_{p_1}^1 \otimes \dots \otimes \hat{O}_{p_N}^N \quad (3)$$

Here S means symmetrization, $p = \{p_1, \dots, p_N\}$ is an ordered set of indices 1, 2, 3 and 4 such, that each of indices 1, 2, 3 and 4 appears α , β , γ and δ times respectively; $\hat{O}_{p_i}^i = \hat{u}_i, \hat{d}_i, \hat{s}_i$ or \hat{c}_i at $p_i = 1, 2, 3$ or 4 respectively (here \hat{O}^i acts on the state of i th atom), and

$$C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} = \frac{(\alpha + \beta + \gamma + \delta)!}{\alpha! \cdot \beta! \cdot \gamma! \cdot \delta!} \quad (4)$$

is a number of summands (this is a straightforward generalization of binomial coefficient).

2 Master equation

After adiabatic elimination of the cavity field, the master equation may be written as After adiabatic elimination of the cavity field, the master equation for the system of 2-level atoms with incoherent pumping with the cavity field may be written as

$$\frac{d\hat{\rho}}{dt} = -i\Delta \left[\hat{E}\hat{\rho} - \hat{\rho}\hat{E} \right] + \sum_j \left[\gamma_s \hat{\mathcal{D}}[\hat{\sigma}_{ge}^j] \hat{\rho} + R \hat{\mathcal{D}}[\hat{\sigma}_{eg}^j] \hat{\rho} + \nu \hat{\mathcal{D}}[\hat{\sigma}_{ee}^j] \hat{\rho} \right] + \frac{4g^2}{\kappa} \hat{\mathcal{D}}[\hat{X}] \hat{\rho}, \quad (5)$$

where $\hat{X} = \sum_j \hat{\sigma}_{ge}^j$, Δ is detuning of the atomic transition from the cavity resonant frequency, γ_s , R and γ_R are spontaneous decay rate, pumping rate and decoherence rate respectively, κ is the decay rate of the energy of the cavity field.

It is convenient to introduce operators

$$\hat{E} = \sum_{j=1}^N \hat{\sigma}_{ee}^j, \quad \hat{G} = \sum_{j=1}^N \hat{\sigma}_{gg}^j \quad (6)$$

and superoperators

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{E}_L \hat{\rho} &= \hat{E} \hat{\rho}, & \hat{E}_R \hat{\rho} &= \hat{\rho} \hat{E}, & \hat{E}_{LR} \hat{\rho} &= \sum_{j=1}^N \hat{\sigma}_{ee}^j \hat{\rho} \hat{\sigma}_{ee}^j \\ \hat{G}_L \hat{\rho} &= \hat{G} \hat{\rho}, & \hat{G}_R \hat{\rho} &= \hat{\rho} \hat{G}, & \hat{B} \hat{\rho} &= \sum_{j=1}^N \hat{\sigma}_{ge}^j \hat{\rho} \hat{\sigma}_{eg}^j, \\ \hat{X}_L \hat{\rho} &= \hat{X} \hat{\rho}, & \hat{X}_L^+ \hat{\rho} &= \hat{X}^+ \hat{\rho}, & \hat{T} \hat{\rho} &= \sum_{j=1}^N \hat{\sigma}_{eg}^j \hat{\rho} \hat{\sigma}_{ge}^j, \\ \hat{X}_R \hat{\rho} &= \hat{\rho} \hat{X}, & \hat{X}_R^+ \hat{\rho} &= \hat{\rho} \hat{X}^+. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Using superoperators (7), one may rewrite the master equation (5) as

$$\frac{d\rho}{dt} = \hat{A}\rho \quad \text{where} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{A} = & -i\Delta [\hat{E}_L - \hat{E}_R] - \frac{\gamma_{sp}}{2} [\hat{E}_L + \hat{E}_R - 2\hat{B}] - \frac{R}{2} [\hat{G}_L + \hat{G}_R - 2\hat{T}] \\ & - \frac{\nu}{2} [\hat{E}_L + \hat{E}_R - 2\hat{E}_{LR}] - \frac{2g^2}{\kappa} [\hat{X}_L^+ \hat{X}_L + \hat{X}_R \hat{X}_R^+ - 2\hat{X}_R^+ \hat{X}_L] \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

3 Matrix elements of superoperators

The density matrix $\hat{\rho}$ is expanded into elementary matrices $\hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$ with coefficients $\rho_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$. To calculate matrix elements of superoperators (7), one has to find how these superoperators acts on $\hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$. Consider, for example, $\hat{X}_L \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$:

$$\hat{X}_L \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} = \hat{X} \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} = \sum_{j=1}^N \hat{\sigma}_{ge}^j \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} = \sum_{j=1}^N \hat{1}^1 \otimes \dots \otimes \hat{c}^j \otimes \hat{1}^{j+1} \otimes \dots \otimes \hat{1}^{j+1} \cdot \frac{1}{C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}} \sum_p \left(\dots \hat{O}_p^j \dots \right). \quad (10)$$

The specific term in this double sum corresponding to some fixed atom j and to some ordered set p of indices 1, 2, 3 and 4 appearing α, β, γ and δ times respectively contains $\hat{c}_j \cdot \hat{O}_p^j$, where $\hat{O}_p^j \in \{\hat{u}^j, \hat{d}^j, \hat{c}^j, \hat{s}^j\}$. Using $\hat{c}\hat{u} = \hat{c}$, $\hat{c}\hat{d} = 0$, $\hat{c}\hat{s} = \hat{d}$ and $\hat{c}\hat{c} = 0$, we can write $\hat{X}_L \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} = C_1 \hat{P}_{\alpha-1, \beta, \gamma, \delta+1} + C_2 \hat{P}_{\alpha, \beta+1, \gamma-1, \delta}$, where the coefficients C_1 and C_2 are the numbers of terms where $\hat{O} = \hat{u}$ and $\hat{O} = \hat{s}$ respectively divided by $\hat{C}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$. One may find that, for example, that $C_1 = C_{\alpha-1, \beta, \gamma, \delta} \times N / C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$, where $C_{\alpha-1, \beta, \gamma, \delta}$ is a number of sets p with $\hat{O}_p^j = u$, and N comes from summation over j . such terms at any fixed j , and summation over j gives another factor N . Therefore, $C_1 = \alpha$. Similarly, $C_2 = \gamma$, and

$$\hat{X}_L \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} = \alpha \cdot \hat{P}_{\alpha-1, \beta, \gamma, \delta+1} + \gamma \cdot \hat{P}_{\alpha, \beta+1, \gamma-1, \delta}. \quad (11)$$

Action of other superoperators (7) on $\hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$ can be found in the same manner. It gives

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{E}_L \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} &= (\alpha + \gamma) \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}, & \hat{G}_L \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} &= (\beta + \delta) \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}, & \hat{T} \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} &= \beta \hat{P}_{\alpha+1, \beta-1, \gamma, \delta} \\ \hat{E}_R \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} &= (\alpha + \delta) \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}, & \hat{G}_R \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} &= (\beta + \gamma) \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}, & \hat{B} \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} &= \alpha \hat{P}_{\alpha-1, \beta+1, \gamma, \delta} \\ \hat{X}_L \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} &= \alpha \hat{P}_{\alpha-1, \beta, \gamma, \delta+1} + \gamma \hat{P}_{\alpha, \beta+1, \gamma-1, \delta}, & \hat{X}_R \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} &= \beta \hat{P}_{\alpha, \beta-1, \gamma, \delta+1} + \gamma \hat{P}_{\alpha+1, \beta, \gamma-1, \delta} \\ \hat{X}_L^+ \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} &= \beta \hat{P}_{\alpha, \beta-1, \gamma+1, \delta} + \delta \hat{P}_{\alpha+1, \beta, \gamma, \delta-1}, & \hat{X}_R^+ \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} &= \alpha \hat{P}_{\alpha-1, \beta, \gamma+1, \delta} + \delta \hat{P}_{\alpha, \beta+1, \gamma, \delta-1}, \\ \hat{E}_{LR} \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} &= \alpha \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

From (12) one can easily get matrix elements of all the superoperators necessary to construct the matrix of evolution superoperator \hat{A} (9). Spectrum of the bad-cavity laser can be found as a Fourier transform of real part of two-time correlation function $\langle \hat{a}^+(t) \hat{a}(0) \rangle$, where

$$\hat{a} = -\frac{2ig}{\kappa} \hat{X}_L. \quad (13)$$

what, in turn, can be calculated with the help of quantum regression theorem [2]. At $\Delta = 0$, one can just approximate $\langle \hat{a}^+(t)\hat{a}(0) \rangle$ by $n \exp(-\lambda t)$, and estimate the spectral linewidth $\Delta\omega$ as $\Delta\omega \approx 2\lambda$.

4 Model without adiabatic elimination of the cavity field

If the cavity decay rate κ is of the same order of magnitude as another evolution rates in the system, one can not perform adiabatic elimination of the cavity field \hat{a} , and has to keep it explicitly. One may use, for example, truncated Fock state to describe cavity degrees of freedom. Then the density matrix can be represented as

$$\hat{\rho} = \sum_{m,n} \sum_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \rho_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta, nm} \hat{P}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \otimes |n\rangle \langle m|, \quad (14)$$

where the master equation has the form (8) with

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{A} = & -i\Delta \left[\hat{E}_L - \hat{E}_R \right] - ig \left(\hat{a}_L^+ \hat{X}_L - \hat{X}_R \hat{a}_R^+ + \hat{X}_L^+ \hat{a}_L - \hat{a}_R \hat{X}_R^+ \right) - \frac{\gamma_{sp}}{2} \left[\hat{E}_L + \hat{E}_R - 2\hat{B} \right] - \frac{R}{2} \left[\hat{G}_L + \hat{G}_R - 2\hat{T} \right] \\ & - \frac{\nu}{2} \left[\hat{E}_L + \hat{E}_R - 2\hat{E}_{LR} \right] - \frac{\kappa}{2} \left(\hat{a}_L^+ \hat{a}_L + \hat{a}_R \hat{a}_R^+ - 2\hat{a}_L \hat{a}_R^+ \right), \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where $\hat{a}_L \hat{\rho} = \hat{a} \hat{\rho}$, $\hat{a}_R \hat{\rho} = \hat{\rho} \hat{a}$, $\hat{a}_L^+ \hat{\rho} = \hat{a}^+ \hat{\rho}$, $\hat{a}_R^+ \hat{\rho} = \hat{\rho} \hat{a}^+$, and other superoperators are defined in (7).

References

- [1] Stephan Hartmann. Generalized dicke states, 2012.
- [2] M.O. Scully and M.S. Zubairy. *Quantum optics*. Cambridge University Press, 1997.